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No News Is Good News Testing Modality and Redundancy in Immersive Augmented Reality

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ABSTRACT

Background: The modality and redundancy principles are well-established within the cognitive theory of multimedia learning for their effectiveness in traditional media. However, previous studies applying these principles in virtual reality have shown contradictory results when immersive technologies are involved.

Objectives: This study investigates the effects of modality and redundancy principles from the cognitive theory of multimedia learning on cognitive load and learning outcomes in head-mounted display augmented reality.

Methods: Using a between-subjects experimental design, 104 male participants were randomly assigned to three conditions based on the way verbal instructions related to a T-shirt folding procedure were presented (audio-only, text-only, text-and-audio). The presentation of the verbal instructions served as the manipulated variable; cognitive load levels and participants' performance were measured as outcome variables. Bayesian analyses were conducted to verify that there were no significant differences between the text-and-audio group and the audio-only group, and a Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) examined the relationship between the experimental condition, cognitive load levels, and participants' performance.

Results and Conclusions: Results support the validity of the modality principle in head-mounted display augmented reality, showing that applying the modality principle significantly decreases intrinsic cognitive load and improves learning performances. The null hypothesis was supported by comparing audio-only and text-and-audio conditions for both cognitive load and learning outcomes. These findings suggest that cognitive theory of multimedia learning principles work similarly in head-mounted display augmented reality as in traditional media, and they offer valuable insights into multimedia learning in immersive augmented reality, extending our understanding of how these principles function in immersive technologies. Contradicting results using immersive technologies could be explained by considering task complexity and perceived intrinsic cognitive load; however, further studies testing different learning materials are necessary to support this hypothesis.

1 | Introduction

Augmented reality (AR) is a technology that overlays digital information (e.g., 3D models, holograms, text) onto the real world in real time (Azuma 1997; Carmigniani et al. 2010; Mann et al. 2023). Its effectiveness in supporting knowledge and skill

is highlighted by a meta-analysis spanning 2012–2021, in which Chang et al. (2022) reported a medium-large effect size ($g = 0.65$) favouring AR compared to traditional media. This result aligns with Yu (2023), who found even stronger effects ($d = 1.01$) in the decade 2012–2022. While AR's benefit over traditional methods seems evident, this advantage may be partially reduced if

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Summary

- What is currently known about this topic
 - Augmented Reality (AR) enhances learning over traditional methods; meta-analyses show significant effects.
 - AR's impact on cognitive load (CL) varies by task type, with procedural tasks lowering CL more than declarative tasks.
 - The Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning (CTML) outlines principles to optimise CL (e.g., modality, redundancy).
 - Limited studies address how CTML principles apply to AR via Head-Mounted Displays (HMD-AR).
- What this paper adds
 - This study examines the modality principle and redundancy principle in HMD-AR for procedural learning.
 - Redundancy did not harm outcomes.
 - Modality was confirmed: audio-only and audio + text yielded better performance than text-only.
 - The reversed modality principle effect found in virtual reality studies may be due to the high levels of perceived intrinsic CL in the selected tasks.
- Implications for practise and/or policy
 - Designers should favour audio narration over text to reduce load and improve efficiency in HMD-AR.
 - Educators using HMD-AR should align materials with multimedia principles, not assuming redundancy impairs outcomes.
 - AR developers should apply CTML principles in their applications.
 - Policymakers integrating HMD-AR must consider CLT and CTML for efficient cognitive processing.

AR is compared to other experimental conditions (Candido et al. 2025).

Despite the demonstrated effectiveness of this technology in supporting learning, however, it is not yet clear whether it produces higher levels of cognitive load (CL) in those who use it for learning. Studies on AR indicate that its impact on CL varies by learning type—with lower levels observed during procedural tasks compared to declarative learning (Buchner et al. 2021b). At the same time, it might be plausible to hypothesise that it is not the technology itself that determines CL levels, but rather the good or poor design of the learning materials (Buchner et al. 2021a). The cognitive theory of multimedia learning (CTML) proposes principles to optimise CL in learning materials, validated in traditional media (Mayer 2020) and video (Mayer 2021). Implementing these principles can plausibly minimise extraneous cognitive load (ECL; Candido et al. 2025). However, few studies (Çeken and Taşkın 2022) have tested their effectiveness in AR. The lack of studies becomes even more relevant when looking at AR experienced with head-mounted displays (HMD), which so far has been tested mainly in usability studies (e.g.,

Baumeister et al. 2017) and not for real learning tasks (Thees et al. 2020; Candido and Cattaneo 2025; Candido et al. 2025).

To date, most research on HMD-based design according to CTML principles has focused on virtual reality (VR; Makransky 2021). Although VR and AR are often grouped under 'immersive technologies', some core CTML principles have yet to be replicated in VR. In particular, the 'modality principle', which states that in multimedia learning, people learn better when words are presented in auditory rather than textual format (Mayer 2020), has not been verified when using immersive VR (Lieberman and Dubovi 2022). In Albus and Seufert (2023), the modality effect was reversed: textual information yielded better learning than auditory presentation. Similarly, the 'redundancy principle'—which posits that adding printed text to graphics and narration does not improve learning—has not been confirmed in immersive VR (Baceviciute et al. 2021). Liu et al. (2021) even found that the presentation of redundant materials in the use of immersive VR led to better learning outcomes. Due to the lack of studies that have investigated these principles in HMD-AR and the discrepancy with CTML, we have developed a study aimed at testing the modality and redundancy principles when using HMD-AR supported by Microsoft HoloLens 2. In the following paragraphs, we will present the cognitive load theory (CLT), the CTML, and then delve into the presentation of the modality and redundancy principles.

1.1 | Cognitive Load Theory

CLT is based on the idea that we have a limited amount of cognitive resources to process information and learn (Sweller 1988; Sweller et al. 2019). Our processing capacity is primarily limited by working memory, which processes information using various resources: visuospatial sketchpad, phonological loop, and episodic buffer (Baddeley 2012).

According to CLT, there are three types of cognitive load: intrinsic cognitive load (ICL), ECL, and germane cognitive load (GCL). ICL represents the perceived complexity of the task, influenced by prior knowledge and memory skills, with an objective component determined by the interactivity of elements: The more the learning of information depends on understanding previous information, the more complex the material will be (Sweller and Chandler 1994). ECL is the load imposed by the way information is presented: The more efficient the presentation method, the lower the ECL levels, allowing more resources to be dedicated to learning itself (Sweller et al. 1998). The concept of GCL has been reconceptualised in recent years (Sweller et al. 2019). Initially defined as the cognitive load imposed to create a relationship between previous and new knowledge (Sweller et al. 1998), it is now seen as a process that redistributes cognitive resources from ECL to ICL, rather than as a distinct type of cognitive load (Greenberg and Zheng 2022). Optimal management of these types of cognitive load is essential for effective learning. Reducing ECL through efficient information presentation allows more resources to be dedicated to processing ICL, thus facilitating learning. This concept aligns with the CTML, which suggests principles aimed at optimising ICL while minimising ECL. Among the tested principles, the modality and redundancy principles play a crucial role in determining how verbal instructions are provided to learners.

1.2 | The Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning and Its Modality and Redundancy Principles

CTML is an evidence-based theory that has tested a series of principles aimed at optimising the creation of learning materials (Mayer 2001, 2014, 2020). This theory has developed principles to minimise extraneous processing (related to ECL), optimise essential processing (related to ICL), and promote generative processing (related to GCL). In our application, several principles were applied to optimise learning, but they did not differ across the different versions of the application itself (see Section 2.1 for details). On the contrary, we implemented the principles of modality and redundancy in a different way.

1.2.1 | Modality Principle

The modality principle states that in multimedia explanations, words should be presented as auditory narration rather than as on-screen text (Moreno and Mayer 1999). This principle is based on Paivio's (1990) dual-channel theory and supported by physiological evidence, such as the ERP study by Welcome et al. (2011). Ginns (2005) conducted a meta-analysis showing that presenting information as text and images is less effective than combining audio and images. The modality effect reports higher effect sizes with high element interactivity learning materials, where high ICL levels are achieved ($d=0.63$). For low ICL learning materials, no effects were found ($d=0.10$). The modality effect produces a large effect size when learning materials are system-paced ($d=0.93$) but disappears when students control the pace ($d=-0.14$) compared to text-based instructions. Students likely use strategies such as first looking at images and then reading text, reducing the benefits of simultaneous audio-visual presentation. However, limitations like the 'transient information effect' (Leahy and Sweller 2011) occur when auditory information is too complex or lengthy, especially when learning materials are not segmented (Mayer 2020). The implementation of the modality principle in videos enhances learning compared to visual material alone. Mayer (2021) reported that four studies consistently showed better learning outcomes when the modality principle was applied compared to text instructions ($d=1.02$), thus further confirmed in a recent study (Haavisto et al. 2023). The robustness of the research on traditional multimedia suggests that the modality principle can be applied to immersive media. Moreover, CTML suggests that the modality principle is effective in optimising levels of essential processing, which—while not constituting an exact equivalent—represents the theoretical counterpart of ICL within CLT. For this reason, it is reasonable to assume that implementing the modality principle could significantly reduce ICL levels and, consequently, lead to improved learning outcomes; in other words, it is plausible that the modality principle can make the comprehension of instructions considerably easier.

1.2.2 | Redundancy Principle

The redundancy principle, closely related to the modality principle, posits that learning could be hindered when identical information is presented in auditory and text format simultaneously (Mayer 2001; Sweller 2005). Redundancy can increase ECL, as learners may spend additional resources to exclude one of the

two information sources, thereby reducing the resources available for essential processing (Sweller et al. 2011). However, the effect of redundancy can be moderated by various factors. For instance, when students control the pace of the presentation or have high prior domain knowledge, the effect can be reduced or even reversed (Kalyuga et al. 2004). Additionally, in some situations, such as learning a foreign language or dealing with complex technical terms, redundant information presentation can actually benefit learning (Mayer and Johnson 2008).

Although, from a theoretical standpoint, the simultaneous presentation of the same information could increase ECL levels and thus worsen learning outcomes, current evidence seems to support the idea that duplicating the source of information does not produce either positive or negative effects. A meta-analysis conducted by Adesope and Nesbit (2012) highlighted that redundancy is generally ineffective when identical content is presented both as text and audio compared to text alone ($g=-0.04$). When the correspondence between text and audio is high, the effect size is very small, though still statistically significant, favouring the presentation that includes both text and audio ($g=0.21$). However, presenting the same content in both audio and text is effective when the text serves a summarising purpose ($g=0.99$) compared to text alone. In fact, the recent definition provided by Mayer (2020, 186) states that "People do not learn better when printed text is added to graphic and narration. People learn better from graphic, narration and printed text, when the lesson is fast paced."

1.2.3 | Boundary Conditions for Modality and Redundancy Principles

These principles must be analysed also in light of various possible intervening variables. For example, Schnotz (2021) emphasises that the modality principle becomes particularly effective when animations, not just images, are combined with verbal information, as in the case of our study. Moreover, the level of complexity of the verbal instructions can significantly influence the effectiveness of the modality principle. Indeed, as the complexity of verbal material increases, it may become relevant to have written material available that allows learners to read key passages again more carefully (Leahy and Sweller 2011). In their experiment, the authors demonstrated that when verbal instructions were long and unsegmented, participants achieved worse performance in the transfer task. Conversely, when segmenting was restored, the modality effect became observable again, with participants in the text-only condition being outperformed by participants in the audio condition. On the other hand, trivial tasks might not benefit from the application of the modality principle (Leahy et al. 2003). It is necessary to find a balance with tasks that require intermediate levels of ICL without incurring very high interactivity in learning materials (Ginns 2005). Prior knowledge level is another important factor; several studies have demonstrated that having high levels of prior knowledge can make the presentation of multiple media for the same information a possible cause of split attention, thereby resulting in performance impairment (Kalyuga 2007). It is well known that as participants' expertise increases, it is appropriate to present as little information as possible because listening to instructions that coincide with already known information or

that partially contradict already known information creates a form of extraneous cognitive load, as demonstrated in the longitudinal study conducted by Kalyuga et al. (2000). In their article, Chen et al. (2016) revisited the expertise reversal effect principle by unifying it with the concept of element interactivity of intrinsic cognitive load. In other words, for more expert participants, the level of element interactivity is much lower, and for this reason they can achieve better performance without receiving instructions that they do not need to complete the task. Other additional factors include learner characteristics such as working memory capacity (Schüler et al. 2011); having greater working memory resources makes it less likely that the subject will find themselves in a cognitive overload condition. Finally, when testing the modality and redundancy principles, it is also essential to control for the correct application of the spatial and temporal contiguity principles (Ginns 2006). In the case of our study, all participants had never learned the T-shirt folding technique before and for this reason could be considered novices, the presentation of instructions was done by applying the segmenting principle, the verbal instructions were presented as simply as possible, and finally the spatial and temporal contiguity principles were applied throughout the application to avoid forms of ECL not dictated by redundancy alone from influencing the results.

1.2.4 | Modality and Redundancy Principles in Immersive Technologies

The advent of immersive technologies has made it necessary to investigate the effectiveness of CTML principles already established in the literature, applying them to the new context of immersive media. The specific role of immersive technology in supporting learning has been recognised with the introduction of the immersive principle (Makransky 2021). However, knowledge of the actual impact these technologies can have on learning is still in its infancy, as evidenced by the very definition of the principle: “People do not necessarily learn better with higher immersion media (such as immersive virtual reality) than lower immersion media (such as onscreen video)” (Mayer and Fiorella 2021, 14).

Substantial differences, however, emerge between AR and VR. VR, by immersing the user in a completely new environment, can induce a more pronounced estrangement effect than AR. The latter, in fact, merely adds a digital information layer to the real world, allowing students to interact with an environment that remains familiar. This reduces the distracting potential linked to the need to adapt to a new context, even following a familiarisation phase with the technology. A further advantage of AR lies in the more natural interaction it allows: the user learns by interacting with the real world in the way they are already accustomed to, without the mediation of joysticks or specific gestures, which are often necessary in VR. This does not, however, preclude the possibility that VR could achieve such high levels of simulation as to make interaction with virtual worlds, for learning purposes, entirely comparable to interaction with the real world. Ultimately, it is plausible that AR could benefit from the modality principle to an equal or greater extent than traditional media. The ability to present contextualised animations directly in the real environment, in conjunction with

an explanatory audio narration, could represent a decisive advantage. This approach proves particularly promising for procedural learning, which is why the present study was designed to allow participants to listen to instructions whilst interacting directly with the physical environment, an approach that, to the best of our knowledge, had not yet been directly tested, as in previous studies on AR the procedural instructions were still provided in written form (Ariansyah et al. 2022; Gonnermann-Müller et al. 2024).

Not all principles, however, may be affected in the same way by the advent of immersive technologies. While the validity of principles such as signalling, spatial contiguity, and temporal contiguity (Altmeyer et al. 2020; Candido and Cattaneo 2025; Candido et al. 2025; Thees et al. 2020) could be strongly influenced by the rise of AR, it might be reasonable not to expect significant differences for other principles, such as the pre-training principle or the segmenting principle (Çeken and Taşkın 2024; Lawson and Mayer 2024).

It may be sensible to first examine the principles most likely to be affected by the technical affordances of immersive technologies, or to investigate those that have already demonstrated significant differences in other immersive media, such as VR. This is the case for the modality and redundancy principles, which have been investigated in numerous studies using VR but remain unexplored in the context of immersive AR. Given the limited research on these principles in AR environments, examining VR studies provides valuable insights into how immersive technologies might interact with modality and redundancy principles, offering a foundation for understanding their potential application in AR contexts. For example, Liberman and Dubovi (2022) used a pre-post research design to test acquired theoretical and procedural knowledge. The authors had participants performing a preliminary procedure for drug administration in an IVR environment, guiding them with textual or auditory instructions. The results showed that subjects in the text-only condition paid attention to the most salient areas for learning the task, such as medications, and took significantly fewer attempts to recognise them compared to the group receiving audio-only instructions. However, comparing the post-test in the two conditions, no significant difference was identified. Although the text-only modality did not achieve significantly better results compared to the audio-only modality in the final knowledge test, the text-only condition obtained better performance compared to the audio-only condition, partially contradicting the effectiveness of the modality principle. The results, however, may have been influenced by differences in the time taken by participants for the different conditions, as this variable was not controlled. The results obtained in the knowledge test, on the other hand, were entirely consistent with the fact that students could perform the procedure at their own pace and the control of the activity was not dictated by the system (Ginns 2005). Finally, although the researcher did not administer any perceived ICL scale, he reported that the participants with audio narration had a significantly larger number of electrodermal activity peaks, when compared to the participants who read the instructions, thus suggesting that the participants preferred reading rather than listening, which is coherent with the observed learning outcomes.

In the study conducted by Albus and Seufert (2023), the modality principle was reversed. The researchers showed the same learning material with visual content in IVR using two modalities: audio-only and text-only. To reduce ECL, areas of interest were highlighted in both conditions. Exactly the same information was provided in both conditions. The reported results showed significantly better learning in the text condition, both in the retention and in the transfer tasks. No difference was reported for any of the CL components. However, these results may have been influenced by the transient effect (Leahy and Sweller 2011). In fact, although the material was self-paced, participants in the audio-only condition may not have listened to the content entirely. Furthermore, as suggested by the authors, subjects in the text-only condition may have read the text more than once, although controlling for the time spent, no significant differences were identified between the two conditions. It remains possible that, given the same amount of time, students in the text-only condition were able to read multiple times compared to the single listening done in the audio-only condition. Another possible explanation for the results is dictated by the perceived ICL. In fact, the participants reported that they found the learning materials particularly complex: the ICL levels were clearly beyond the median, thus suggesting that the participants could have preferred to have the opportunity to re-read the more difficult sections of the verbal instructions.

In the study conducted by Baceviciute et al. (2021), three different IVR conditions were compared: audio-only, text-only, and text-and-audio. The learning task involved learning a series of information about osteosarcoma. The content was divided into 24 blocks of information ranging from 300 to 400 characters. The results showed that participants in the audio-only condition performed significantly worse than those in the text-only or text-and-audio condition in the retention task. No significant difference was found in the transfer task. Self-reported CL levels showed a significant difference between conditions for ECL levels. These results are coherent with the performance reported in the retention task. However, an interesting discrepancy emerged when examining physiological measures: the CL levels detected via EEG showed significantly lower levels in the audio condition compared to the text-only and text-and-audio conditions, which would typically suggest more efficient processing according to the modality principle, despite the poorer behavioural performance. The differences found in the retention task may have been dictated by the fact that, although participants exercised control in moving to the next block of information, they still had no control over the audio content: They could neither pause it, nor fast-forward or rewind it. Moreover, unlike the previous study, although the learning material had a total duration of about 15 min, it was not indicated whether there was a difference in times across the different conditions. Finally, also for this study, a high level of ICL was perceived by the participants while performing the learning task, suggesting that the participants could have preferred the written verbal instructions due to the complexity.

These results, although not definitive, indicate that the modality principle does not always constitute an advantage for learning when using VR. Indeed, in some circumstances, it can represent a disadvantage when compared with a purely textual presentation or with a combination of text and narration. However,

certain limitations in the research design of the analysed studies and the possibility that participants in the textual condition may have re-read the learning material multiple times raise doubts that could explain the apparent inconsistency with the modality and redundancy principles or the rise of a 'reversed modality effect' (Albus and Seufert 2023). Furthermore, the high levels of ICL are a common pattern in two out of the three analysed studies; also, the reverse effect observed in the results could be explained solely by the task complexity and not by the immersion offered by the VR environment.

Turning to AR research, such critical issues do not seem to emerge systematically but rather appear to be linked to the design of individual studies (Buchner et al. 2021b). While recent studies have begun exploring CTML principles in AR contexts, revealing both potential advantages and challenges compared to established media (Candido and Cattaneo 2025; Candido et al. 2025; Gonnermann-Müller and Krüger 2024), comprehensive investigations of modality and redundancy principles specifically in immersive AR remain limited. A recent study by Çeken and Taşkın (2024) examined the effectiveness of the modality, segmenting, and pre-training principles in learning environments based on immersive VR and smartphone-based AR. The results related to the modality principle indicated that the effect of the modality principle was significant only in the AR environment and for the low-complexity learning task (lightning formation), whereas it was not found either in the more complex task (cell structure) or in the other learning environments. Also in this case the results are consistent with the idea that the modality principle only applies with low complexity tasks; in fact, the participants who benefited from the modality principle were those who reported low ICL levels (3.49 out of 11), but it already did not apply with the cell structure learning material (4.64 out of 11). Although this study has expanded the knowledge on the effectiveness of CTML principles in the use of immersive technologies, these principles, including the modality principle, have not yet been tested for immersive AR. In other words, although the modality principle appears to be effective in the use of handheld AR, it is not known whether the same can be observed in immersive environments and whether the presentation of redundant materials could constitute a possible disadvantage for learning. Therefore, while VR research provides important insights into how immersive technologies might interact with modality and redundancy principles, dedicated research on immersive AR remains essential to understand whether the patterns observed in VR apply to this distinct medium.

1.3 | Aims, Research Questions and Hypotheses

The objective of this study is to verify to what extent the modality and the redundancy principles apply to HMD-AR. Although these principles are well established in traditional media, there is a significant research gap regarding their applicability to immersive technology, especially HMD-AR. Our main research questions are the following:

RQ1. *How does the redundancy principle apply in the context of HMD-AR in terms of its effects on performance and ECL?*

RQ2. *How does the modality principle apply in the context of HMD-AR in terms of its effects on performance and ICL?*

FIGURE 1 | Tested model. Condition modality = condition where the modality principle has been applied; ICL = intrinsic cognitive load; number of attempts = number of folding attempts assisted by AR.

To answer these research questions we compared three experimental conditions in which participants were taught how to fold a T-shirt using a specific technique that could benefit from the affordances of HMD-AR. The three experimental conditions did not differ in any respect except for the presentation of the verbal instructions: one group received the instructions only in text, one group only in audio (thus applying the modality principle), and one group received exactly the same instructions in both audio and text format (redundant). Considering the contradictory results between early HMD-VR studies and classical literature, we formulated the following related hypotheses (distinguished per principle; an additional control hypothesis for the folding accuracy is also presented).

1.3.1 | Redundancy Principle

H1. *Audio-only and text-and-audio conditions will be significantly similar to each other in terms of CL and all performance outcomes.*

As suggested in the meta-analysis conducted by Adesope and Nesbit (2012), when text and audio are completely redundant, no significant differences are expected both in terms of performance and CL—particularly ECL. In our case, performance is defined as the success of failure in the guided task using the technology as well as the results obtained in the retention task and transfer tasks (see procedure in Section 2.3 for detail).

1.3.2 | Modality Principle

The modality principle was tested using the model shown in Figure 1. In addition to reporting the mediation of ICL on learning outcomes, as suggested by theory (Mayer 2020), we also reported the number of attempts. This measure provides an indication of how effectively the instructions were understood by the participants. The instructions were given only once per each attempt. Having to make more attempts corresponds to poorer comprehension of the instructions.

H2. *ICL levels will be significantly lower in the audio-only and text-and-audio conditions when compared to the text condition.*

The modality principle is one of the principles aimed at optimising essential processing corresponding to ICL in the CLT (Mayer 2020), therefore we expect a significant reduction in ICL levels when the principle is applied.

H3. *Higher levels of ICL will lead to worse learning outcomes—in terms of success in the guided task, the retention task, and the three transfer tasks—and will require more attempts before learning the task.*

Applying the modality principle determines better learning outcomes (Ginns 2005). According to CTML (Mayer 2020) this should be mediated by essential processing (corresponding to ICL in CLT). Success in folding the T-shirt is determined by whether the participant actually folded the T-shirt using the taught technique. The evaluation is dichotomous; the accuracy with which the T-shirt was folded is not taken into account.

H4. *Participants who needed more attempts to complete the folding will have worse performance in successfully completing all the folding tasks.*

We believe that having to listen to the instructions multiple times could be a further indication that the instructions were not entirely clear. Success or failure in folding the T-shirt is determined by assessing whether the T-shirt was folded using the taught technique.

1.3.3 | Control Hypothesis

H5. *No significant differences in terms of accuracy.*

Since accuracy is entirely dependent on the animations, which are the same across all conditions, we do not expect any difference. Accuracy is determined by comparing a perfectly folded

FIGURE 2 | Differences in the presentation modality of verbal information.

T-shirt, using the same taught technique, with the T-shirt folded by the participants. Six different measures were used. A more detailed description is provided in Section 2.3.

2 | Materials and Methods

To test our hypotheses, we conducted a between-subjects study with three experimental conditions (see Figure 2): (1) audio-only: Verbal instructions provided only by voice, (2) text-only: Verbal instructions provided only with text, and (3) text-and-audio: Verbal instructions provided with both text and audio, where the text and audio were completely identical and provided simultaneously. All three conditions were supported via visual inputs through an AR application. We chose to have participants learn a T-shirt folding procedure, as this type of task benefits from the implementation in HMD-AR of spatial contiguity, temporal contiguity, and signalling principles. To enable the execution of the procedure, we used a Head Mounted Display device, Microsoft HoloLens 2. The entire application, from text creation to implementation, was developed in line with the principles of CTML (see Section 2.1 for details). The objective was to verify the applicability of the modality principle and the effects of redundancy in HMD-AR learning.

2.1 | Application Development in Line With CTML Principles

Except for the differences created for the three experimental conditions, the three applications were completely identical. The design of the applications was done by applying the main principles of CTML. To reduce ICL, the segmenting principle (Rey et al. 2019) was applied by dividing the task into different phases, as shown in Figures 3 and 4.

To reduce ECL, the coherence principle (Rey 2012) was followed by providing only the information strictly necessary for the completion of each step in the verbal instructions. The spatial contiguity (Schroeder and Cenkci 2020) and temporal contiguity (Ginns 2006) principles were also applied by providing instructions and animations in time and in space. The signalling principle (Alpizar et al. 2020) was applied by using white spheres to highlight the key information in the multimedia lesson, that is, where to place the hands to correctly proceed with the folding of the garment (Figure 5). This was particularly relevant for those steps in which the gesture was difficult to imagine or unfamiliar; animations indeed can be especially helpful for learners when the procedure involves movements that are complex to understand (Ploetzner et al. 2020). Additionally, hand-tracking allowed us to verify the correctness of the execution of the different steps (Figure 6).

FIGURE 3 | The first step of the procedure: Correctly positioning hands on the real T-shirt.

When the information was provided in both text and audio modality, the voice used to deliver the information was a human voice, in line with the voice principle (Craig and Schroeder 2017) although advances in synthetic speech quality have made this distinction less critical (Davis et al. 2019). The choice to select a procedural learning task is intended to leverage the potential added value for learning provided by the affordances offered by HMD-AR; in particular, the possibility of applying the principles of signalling as well as spatial and temporal contiguity directly in the real world when carrying out this task constitutes a tangible added value. Moreover, the opportunity to listen to the instructions while observing the animations or interacting directly with the actual T-shirt represents a significant added value in applying the modality principle. A summary of the applied principles is provided in Table 1.

2.2 | Participants

To evaluate the redundancy principle (H1), we conducted a post hoc Bayesian power analysis using the default Jeffrey-Zellner-Siow cauchy prior ($r = 0.707$) on a collected sample of 104 participants and adopting a decision threshold of $BF_{01} \geq 3$ and 5000 simulations which provides moderate support for the null hypothesis. The analysis was conducted using the R (version 4.4.2) and the library BayesFactor. The resulting estimated power was 0.88. Rather than merely reporting the lack of evidence for a difference—expected given that the textual and audio materials were identical (Adesope and Nesbit 2012)—we aimed to demonstrate that the two conditions were genuinely equivalent. Using the same test, we also examined the control hypothesis concerning the folding accuracy (H5). Although two distinct hypotheses were tested, no

FIGURE 4 | Subsequent steps required to correctly complete the folding of the T-shirt, including moving within three dimensions to ensure proper execution.

FIGURE 5 | Signalling in hand positioning on real T-shirt.

FIGURE 6 | Animation demonstrating the T-shirt folding procedure. *Note:* Real-time hand tracking of the student's hands is displayed on the virtual hands. This information was not visible to the students while executing the procedure but allowed the application to provide feedback when the step was correctly performed.

additional multiplicity adjustment is required for the power analysis (Scott and Berger 2010).

To test the modality principle (H2-H4) a post hoc power analysis was conducted on a sample of 104 participants, analysed

with partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM). Applying Kock and Hadaya's (2016) method, a minimum $|\beta|$ of 0.244 was identified, meaning that lower absolute beta values could lead to Type II error, which occurs when accepting a null hypothesis that is actually false. All participants ($n = 104$) were male students (age range 15–37, $M = 17.2$, $SD = 2.58$) recruited from two vocational schools in the German-speaking region of Switzerland. None had prior HMD-AR experience. The data collection was conducted between October 2023 and January 2024 in an experimental setting, with participants in separate rooms and a one-to-one ratio with the researcher. Participation in the experiment was voluntary, and each participant signed an informed consent form prior to data collection. Participants were randomly assigned to the three conditions, as shown in Table 2.

2.3 | Measures and Instruments

To verify the formulated hypotheses, we measured the success achieved in the learning task, considering three distinct phases: the guided learning, the retention task, and the three transfer tasks phases. CL levels were measured immediately after the learning phase.

2.3.1 | T-Shirt Folding Learning Outcomes

To assess performance, a comprehensive dataset was collected by examining the technology-guided learning procedure, a retention task, and three different transfer tasks. The following four variables were used:

1. The success (1) or failure (0) in correctly folding the T-shirt using the taught technique. One of the necessary conditions for the procedure to be considered correctly performed was that the participant grasped the T-shirt fabric at the two points indicated in Figure 3. Although very simple, this

TABLE 1 | CTML principles implemented in the HMD-AR application.

Principle	Description	References
Principles aimed at reducing ICL		
Segmenting	People learn better when a multimedia message is presented in learner-paced segments rather than as a continuous unit	Rey et al. 2019
Principles aimed at reducing ECL		
Coherence	People learn better when extraneous information is excluded from multimedia lessons	Rey 2012
Spatial Contiguity	Place printed text next to the corresponding part of the graphic	Schroeder and Ceneci 2020
Temporal Contiguity	Present corresponding visual and verbal material at the same time	Ginns 2006
Signalling	People learn better when cues are added that highlight or spotlight the key information in a multimedia lesson and its organisation	Alpizar et al. 2020
Other principles applied		
Voice	People learn better when the words in a multimedia lesson are spoken in an appealing human voice rather than a machine voice	Craig and Schroeder 2017
Animation	People learn better from dynamic graphics than static graphics	Ploetzner et al. 2020

Abbreviations: ECL = extraneous cognitive load; ICL = intrinsic cognitive load.

TABLE 2 | Participant overview per condition.

Condition	Participants	Age (SD)	Age range
Audio	35	17.1 (2.63)	15–30
Text	34	17.7 (3.66)	15–37
Text & Audio	35	16.9 (1.45)	15–22

step was critical for determining the T-shirt's final accuracy, because even small shifts of the hands could create significant asymmetries in the final fold. Next, the collar of the T-shirt had to be aligned with the opposite edge, as shown in step 2 of Figure 4. Once their arms were crossed, participants were required to lift the T-shirt and, while holding the fabric firmly, return to an uncrossed position, as illustrated in step 3 of Figure 4. This step was crucial because participants might release their grip with one hand, which is why it was explicitly emphasised in the instructions. In step 4, the T-shirt was placed back on the surface with the sleeve facing upward, and in step 5 the fold was completed, ensuring that the sleeve was fully covered. If participants achieved similar final folding results without following these five steps, the procedure was still evaluated as a failure; however, obtaining an irregularly folded T-shirt was not considered a failure if all the steps of the procedure had been followed. In the [Annex S1](#) a short video shows the taught procedure.

- The number of content exposures, quantified by counting how many times participants tried the technology assisted procedure before they were able to correctly fold the T-shirt.

- The accuracy of the folding, assessed by measuring the T-shirt at six predefined points, as illustrated in Figure 7, and comparing these measurements with the ideal ones previously obtained on the same T-shirt when ideally folded. To establish the ideal values, all three T-shirts were folded by the researchers using the employed technique. In this case, in addition to using AR, the researchers directly measured each section of the T-shirt to grasp it exactly at the point indicated by the procedure. Once folded, the three T-shirts were measured at the six specified points. None of the T-shirts were washed to avoid differences in the measurements caused by possible cotton shrinkage. The error percentage for each measurement was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Error Percentage } (\Delta_i) = \left(\frac{|\text{Measured Value}_i - \text{Ideal Value}_i|}{\text{Ideal Value}_i} \right) \times 100,$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, 6$

The total error percentage for each folding was obtained by summing the error percentages for each of the six measurements using the summation notation: Total Error Percentage = $\sum_{i=1}^6 \Delta_i$. Finally, to obtain an accuracy score where higher values indicate better precision, we calculated: Accuracy = $100 - (\sum_{i=1}^6 \Delta_i) / 6$. The choice of this formula was dictated by the differences among the various parts of the T-shirt. For example, being off by 1 cm on the collar sides—where the intended length was 3.5 cm—constituted a significant error, whereas being off by 1 cm on the shirt's side length resulted in only a minor inaccuracy. For this reason, the error

FIGURE 7 | Measurements for the quality of folding. A = shoulder right; B = shoulder left; C = shoulder total; D = belly; E = side length 1; F = side length 2.

margin was calculated for each individual measurement rather than relying solely on the raw values. The next step was to subtract the obtained percentages from one hundred so that, instead of interpreting the participants' percentage of inaccuracy, it was possible to interpret their percentage of accuracy, which is easier to understand.

4. The time taken to fold the T-shirt was recorded for each phase. During the learning phase, no time limits were imposed. A time limit of 60 s was set for the retention task and 90 s for the three transfer tasks.

2.3.2 | Cognitive Load

To detect CL levels and differentiate its three components during the learning phase, we used the scale developed and validated by Krieglstein et al. (2023), consisting of 15 items, five per each CL component (ICL, GCL, ECL). The scale was developed to measure the three different components of CL separately; indeed, although the scale was created after the Sweller et al. (2019) article in which GCL was treated as part of ICL, the authors do not deny that only ICL and ECL may affect working memory and, in fact, phrase the items devoted to GCL in an active form. Some examples of GCL items are “I actively reflected upon the learning content” and “I made an effort to understand the learning content.” The ICL and ECL items, by contrast, are phrased to show that the participant is subjected to the learning material design. For ECL, for instance, “The design of the learning material made it difficult to find relevant information quickly,” or for ICL, “The learning content was difficult to understand.” In this case, it seems clear that the participants “underwent” the way the training was structured for them. The CL scale demonstrated good levels of reliability, as shown in Table 3. For the ICL, we removed item number two, increasing the reliability from 0.733 to 0.817.

2.3.3 | Procedure

After signing an informed consent form explaining the purpose of the research and the intended treatment of the collected data, participants were randomly assigned to one of three experimental

TABLE 3 | Reliability test for administered scales.

Measure	ω	95% CI
ICL ^a	0.82	[0.76, 0.87]
ECL	0.81	[0.75, 0.86]
GCL	0.81	[0.76, 0.87]

Abbreviations: ECL = extraneous cognitive load; GCL = germane cognitive load; ICL = intrinsic cognitive load.

^aItem 2 was removed to improve reliability.

conditions (audio only, text only, or text and audio) and instructed on how to use the Microsoft HoloLens 2. Participants calibrated the device following the researcher's instructions to ensure optimal hologram visualisation. Participants learned the T-shirt folding technique during the guided learning phase by first observing the entire procedure in a video displayed directly within the HoloLens 2, and then following a step-by-step guide to complete the procedure. The video was adapted for holographic viewing of the content. In fact, the folded T-shirt shown in the video was identical in every respect—from its dimensions to its colour—to the one participants were expected to learn to fold, and it was projected directly onto the table at precisely the spot where they would later need to fold. The aim was to minimise as much as possible the participant's need to mentally adapt the gesture observed in the video to reality, as if the same real T-shirt had been folded by an instructor to give a preview before showing all the steps more slowly afterward. The researcher was available solely to facilitate the use of the technology (e.g., indicating how to click the start menu of the application using the device's gestures) without supporting or facilitating the T-shirt folding procedure in any way. The researcher timed the participants' completion of the entire guided learning procedure and kept track of the total number of times the content was viewed. Monitoring the number of attempts used by participants was employed to partially compensate for the fact that participants in conditions where text appeared potentially had the opportunity to reread the instructions more than once, whilst participants in the audio condition could only listen to the instructions once. The use of this solution combined with segmenting should have reduced as much as possible the transient effect of verbal content delivered via audio (Leahy and Sweller 2011; Wong et al. 2012). The procedure was interrupted either when participants successfully completed the folding or when they indicated they did not want to continue. In cases where participants were unable to successfully complete the task and decided not to retry the guided learning procedure, the researcher personally demonstrated the solution, excluding them from the retention and transfer tasks but still asking them to complete the questionnaire related to the guided learning task.

After completing the guided learning phase, participants responded to a questionnaire on CL levels. In addition to measuring the variables of interest, this also created a 10-min break between the guided learning task and the subsequent retention task. In the retention task, participants had to repeat the T-shirt folding using the newly learned technique without technology support, within a time limit of 1 min. The researcher, when inviting participants to perform the task, emphasised that despite the time limit, the goal was to fold the T-shirt as accurately as

FIGURE 8 | Representation of the three T-shirts used in the transfer tasks. Transfer 1: child's T-shirt, presented with the same orientation; Transfer 2: same T-shirt, rotated 180°; Transfer 3: larger polo shirt, presented rotated 90°.

possible. The researcher only measured the T-shirt that participants judged to be folded most accurately. Subsequently, they faced three transfer tasks with a time limit of 90s each. Again, the researcher reiterated that the goal was to fold the T-shirt as accurately as possible. The transfer tasks included, in sequence, folding a smaller T-shirt, the same T-shirt used to learn the technique but rotated 180°, and a larger T-shirt in a vertical position (see Figure 8). The entire procedure is summarised in Table 4.

2.3.4 | Data Analysis

To test Hypotheses H1 and H5 we used Jamovi (version 2.4.14); a bayesian Mann–Whitney test was employed to compare the audio and the text and audio conditions (H1). A bayesian ANOVA was employed to compare the accuracy for the three experimental conditions (H5). After confirming support for the null hypothesis between participants in the text-and-audio condition and those in the audio-only condition, we created two groups: the first consisted of participants in the text-only condition, and the second combined participants from both the audio-only and the text-and-audio conditions. These two groups (redundant plus audio-only) were compared with the text-only group. To test H2–H4 we developed a model and tested it with a PLS-SEM. We chose this variance-based technique over a covariance-based SEM because it is less sensitive to sample-size limitations—especially when several variables are included—and therefore requires a more modest sample to test hypotheses. In addition, merging two experimental groups into one produced an unequal sample size between the groups being compared; PLS-SEM handles this imbalance effectively because it is inherently nonparametric (Benitez et al. 2020). We conducted the PLS-SEM analyses with ADANCO (version 2.4.1). We have to highlight that when testing the model with PLS-SEM, however, we removed two items from the ICL sub-scale—items

TABLE 4 | Data collection procedure.

Phase	Description	Time limit
Phase 1: Familiarisation	Instruction on how to wear HoloLens 2 and eye calibration	—
Phase 2: Guided Learning	Learning how to fold the T-shirt, supported by the use of the HMD-AR application. The researcher also acted as a facilitator in using the technology	—
Scale administration	CL (Kriegelstein et al. 2023)	—
Phase 3: Retention ^a	Repetition of the folding without AR support	1 m
Phase 4: Transfer Tasks		—
Transfer Task 1	Folding a child's T-shirt	90s
Transfer Task 2	Folding the same T-shirt learned but rotated 180°	90s
Transfer Task 3	Folding a larger T-shirt in a vertical position	90s

Abbreviations: AR = augmented reality; CL = cognitive load.

^aOnly participants who successfully completed the guided learning phase were admitted to the retention task.

three and four—because, in the context of the model, they appeared to worsen the model's fit. In summary, we first tested the redundancy principle and once we demonstrated that audio only

TABLE 5 | Descriptives divided per condition.

Variable (range)	Condition	N	Mean	SD
ICL (1–9)	Audio only	35	2.2	1.3
	Text only	34	2.9	1.5
	Text & audio	35	2.4	1.1
ECL (1–9)	Audio only	35	2.2	1.3
	Text only	34	2.5	1.4
	Text & audio	35	2.5	1.1
GCL (1–9)	Audio only	35	6.4	1.7
	Text only	34	6.4	1.8
	Text & audio	35	6.2	1.5
Number of attempts (No limitations)	Audio only	35	1.4	0.7
	Text only	33	1.8	0.8
	Text & audio	35	1.4	0.6
Time Guided (No limitations)	Audio only	35	260.9	208.8
	Text only	32	258.7	181.6
	Text & audio	35	231.5	208.6
Result Guided (0%–100%)	Audio only	35	91.4% (32/35)	0.3
	Text only	34	88.2% (30/34)	0.3
	Text & audio	35	91.4% (32/35)	0.3
Result Retention (0%–100%)	Audio only	35	74.3% (26/35)	0.4
	Text only	34	70.6% (24/34)	0.5
	Text & audio	35	85.6% (30/35)	0.3
Result Transfer 1 (0%–100%)	Audio only	35	71.4% (25/35)	0.5
	Text only	34	58.8% (20/34)	0.5
	Text & audio	35	77.1% (27/35)	0.4
Result Transfer 2 (0%–100%)	Audio only	35	68.6% (24/35)	0.4
	Text only	34	61.8% (21/34)	0.5
	Text & audio	35	68.6% (24/35)	0.5
Result Transfer 3 (0%–100%)	Audio only	35	48.6% (17/35)	0.5
	Text only	34	47.1% (16/34)	0.5
	Text & audio	35	60% (21/35)	0.5

(Continues)

TABLE 5 | (Continued)

Variable (range)	Condition	N	Mean	SD
Accuracy Guided (0%–100%)	Audio only	32	89.2%	4.3
	Text only	30	84.8%	7.9
	Text & audio	32	88.1%	6.6
Retention Accuracy (0%–100%)	Audio only	26	82.4%	8.8
	Text only	24	78.2%	15.9
	Text & audio	30	80.4%	8
Transfer 1 Accuracy (0%–100%)	Audio only	25	74.9%	7.1
	Text only	20	77.4%	8.8
	Text & audio	27	78.9%	8.3
Transfer 2 Accuracy (0%–100%)	Audio only	24	77.2%	14.7
	Text only	21	82.5%	9.3
	Text & audio	24	78.2%	9.9
Transfer 3 Accuracy (0%–100%)	Audio only	17	82.8%	7.5
	Text only	16	77.1%	15.7
	Text & audio	21	82.4%	7.5

and text and audio conditions were equivalent, we merged them in a single group. The next step was testing the modality principle by contrasting the text only condition and the newly created group including the audio only and the text and audio conditions. Using the PLS-SEM, we observed the effect determined along the path connecting modality, ICL and learning outcomes.

3 | Results

In the following sections, results are reported in the order of the hypotheses. The results are presented in the following sections according to the formulated hypotheses. Before presenting the results, Table 5 reports the descriptive statistics of the analysed variables divided by condition.

3.1 | Null Hypothesis Support: Audio vs. Text and Audio Conditions All Variables

The results substantially supported hypothesis H1, providing moderate support for the null hypothesis for most of the variables examined. Being in condition audio or text and audio did not make any difference for the variables we observed. For the T-tests, the Mann–Whitney test was used because the data did not meet the normality assumption although the Bayesian approach is less stringent in its assumptions requirements. The results obtained are summarised in Tables 6 and 7.

No differences can be observed along all the tested variables and for most of them, an anecdotal to moderate support for the null hypothesis. Essentially this means we not only demonstrated the absence of significant difference but also established equivalence between the audio only and text and audio conditions.

3.2 | Modality Principle Conditions Outperform Text-Only Condition

The PLS-SEM model included two observed variables (experimental condition and number of attempts to complete the folding task), one latent variable (ICL), and one emergent variable (Folding success) comprising success in the technology-guided task, retention task, and three transfer tasks. To improve model fit, ICL items 3 and 4 were excluded. Table 8 presents the goodness of fit indices for both the saturated and estimated models. The saturated model represents the model when all the possible regressions between variables are imposed, and the estimated model represents the regressions tested. Fit indices have to fulfil the requirements for both. All fit indices fall below their respective HI95, indicating excellent model fit to the data; the standardised root mean square residual (SRMR) represents the differences between the hypothesised model and the collected data. Value below 0.08 are considered acceptable while values below 0.06 are considered good (Hu and Bentler 1999). Our model presented an excellent fit reporting a value of 0.04. The unweighted least-squares discrepancy (d_{ULS}) and the geodesic discrepancy (d_G) represent two unstandardised fit indices. To obtain substantial model fit, the d_{ULS} and d_G should be so small that they could be attributed to sampling error, and thus should not exceed the 95% quantile of the bootstrapped discrepancies (HI_{95}) (Dijkstra and Henseler 2015). In our model, both cases meet the requirements. Instead, the requirements for convergent and divergent validity are always satisfied for the observed variables. Reliability, convergent validity (Dijkstra and Henseler 2015) and discriminant validity (Hair et al. 2021) were good for ICL (see Tables 9 and 10). Finally, loadings for latent and emergent variables are reported in Table 11.

Figure 9 presents the tested model, betas adjusted R^2 values for the explained variance of each variable and f^2 for effect size.

Finally, Table 12 presents the results from the bootstrapped analysis with 5000 resamples, reporting direct and indirect effects.

Overall, the tested model showed that applying the modality principle significantly reduced ICL levels; moreover, the reduction in ICL partially mediated the results obtained in folding the T-shirt. A partial mediation path was identified in the path modality \rightarrow ICL \rightarrow folding performance, whereas a total mediation path was observed in the path modality \rightarrow ICL \rightarrow number of attempts. Finally, the path modality \rightarrow ICL \rightarrow number of attempts \rightarrow folding performance was not confirmed; the number of attempts made did not influence success or failure in folding the T-shirt. In other words, the application of the modality principle significantly reduced ICL levels compared to the text only condition. Experiencing lower levels of ICL increased the participants' success rate in the folding task and significantly reduced the attempts needed to learn the procedure.

3.3 | Accuracy for All Conditions Is Expected to be Comparable

Since the data violated the normality assumptions, the Box-Cox transformation was used to compare accuracy between the different groups. The effectiveness of the transformation was confirmed using Shapiro-Wilk tests for all dependent variables ($p > 0.05$). However, we reported the mean values of the data before the transformation because they are easier to interpret. For both the ANOVA and the Chi-square tests, a non-informative prior was used for the Bayesian analysis. In this case, the data moderately supported the null hypothesis for the possibility of success. However, the result was partially disconfirmed for accuracy in the guided task, where differences between conditions were reported, although they were not significant. Overall, the results offered evidence in support of the null hypothesis, with one exception: in the guided-task accuracy comparison, participants in the modality condition performed significantly better than those in the text-only condition. In the second transfer task, small differences emerged in favour of the text-only condition; however, a BF_{01} close to 1 indicates that, although the performances are not strictly equivalent, they certainly cannot

TABLE 6 | Bayesian test comparing audio and text and audio conditions—continuous variables.

Variable	Test	BF01	Median audio	Median text & audio
ECL	Mann-Whitney U (476)	2.00	2.0	2.6
ICL	Mann-Whitney U (522)	2.84	1.8	2.2
GCL	Mann-Whitney U (671)	3.16	6.6	6.4
GD	Mann-Whitney U (507)	3.89	92.0	92.0
RT	Mann-Whitney U (340)	3.00	85.4	84.4
TR1	Mann-Whitney U (435)	1.14	80.3	82.9
TR2	Mann-Whitney U (276)	3.37	83.3	81.2
TR3	Mann-Whitney U (167)	2.62	86.6	85.1
Number of attempts	Mann-Whitney U (598)	3.47	1.0	1.0
Time guided	Mann-Whitney U (646)	3.80	177.0	167.0

Note: Bayes factor interpretation: $1 < BF_{01} < 3$ anecdotal support for the null hypothesis; $BF_{01} \geq 3$ moderate support for the null hypothesis.

Abbreviations: ECL = extraneous cognitive load; GCL = germane cognitive load; GD = folding accuracy in guided task; ICL = intrinsic cognitive load; number of attempts = number of folding attempts assisted by AR; RT = folding accuracy in retention task; Time guided = time spent to complete the guided phase; TR1 = folding accuracy in transfer task 1; TR2 = folding accuracy in transfer task 2; TR3 = folding accuracy in transfer task 3.

TABLE 7 | Bayesian test comparing audio and text and audio conditions—dichotomic variables.

Result 1–0	Success rate audio	Success rate text & audio	BF ₀₁
Guided	91.4% (32/35)	91.4% (32/35)	3.06
Retention	74.3% (26/35)	85.7% (30/35)	1.11
Transfer 1	71.4% (25/35)	77.1% (27/35)	1.75
Transfer 2	68.6% (24/35)	68.6% (24/35)	1.90
Transfer 3	48.6% (17/35)	60% (21/35)	1.13

Note: Bayes factor interpretation: $1 < BF_{01} < 3$ anecdotal support for the null hypothesis; $BF_{01} \geq 3$ moderate support for the null hypothesis. Abbreviations: Guided = success or failure in T-shirt folding in the guided task; Retention = success or failure in T-shirt folding in the retention task; Transfer 1 = success or failure in T-shirt folding in the Transfer 1 task; Transfer 2 = Success or failure in T-shirt folding in the Transfer 2 task; Transfer 3 = success or failure in T-shirt folding in the Transfer 3 task.

TABLE 8 | Goodness of model fit indices for saturated and estimated models.

Model type	Index	Value	HI95	HI99
Saturated model	SRMR	0.035	0.065	0.075
	dULS	0.066	0.233	0.313
	dG	0.067	0.133	0.235
Estimated model	SRMR	0.041	0.068	0.080
	dULS	0.094	0.256	0.354
	dG	0.076	0.136	0.233

Note: HI interpretation: When performing bootstrapping the difference between your data and the simulation performed must not be significant. HI99 indicates the threshold for non-significance at $p < 0.01$, when your data are below this threshold this means there is not a significant difference (at $p < 0.01$) between your data and your simulation. HI95 indicates the threshold for non-significant at $p < 0.05$, when your data are below this threshold this means there is not a significant difference (at $p < 0.05$) between your data and your simulation. Having values below HI95 means that it is more unlikely that your data differ from the simulation performed. Goodness of fit interpretation: Saturated model = all the possible regression paths are tested. Estimated model = Only the regression paths imposed by the researchers are tested. The saturated model always has a better fit when compared to the tested model. A strong discrepancy between the saturated model and estimated model suggest that a relevant regression was missed in the estimated model. Low discrepancy between saturated and estimated model supports the idea that the tested model is effective and efficient. Abbreviations: dG = geodesic discrepancy ($dG < HI99$ = acceptable fit; $dG < HI95$ = good fit); dULS = unweighted least squares discrepancy ($dULS < HI99$ = acceptable fit; $dULS < HI95$ = good fit); SRMR = Standardised Root Mean Square Residual ($SRMR < 0.08$ = good fit).

TABLE 9 | Construct reliability and convergent validity.

Construct	Dijkstra–Henseler's rho (ρ_A)	Jöreskog's rho (ρ_C)	Cronbach's alpha (α)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Condition modality	1.00	1.00	—	1.00
ICL	0.83	0.82	0.81	0.60
Number of attempts	1.00	1.00	—	1.00

Note: Composite reliability (ρ_C) values in the 0.70–0.90 range indicate adequate internal-consistency reliability, while estimates above 0.95 may reveal redundant indicators (Hair et al. 2021). Dijkstra–Henseler's exact reliability (ρ_A) should likewise fall between 0.70 and 0.90; higher values signal redundancy (Dijkstra and Henseler 2015). Convergent validity is satisfied when the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is ≥ 0.50 (Hair et al. 2021).

be regarded as significantly different. Table 13 summarise the results.

4 | Discussion

This study examined how the modality and redundancy principles apply in HMD-AR when animations are displayed to learn and perform a procedure. We will discuss our results according to the presented hypotheses. We will start by discussing the redundancy principle hypothesis (H1) and then continue with the three hypotheses (H2–H4) on the modality principle. Finally, we will briefly discuss the control hypothesis (H5) on the folding accuracy, which we used to verify whether other possible intervening variables were affecting our main hypotheses on modality and redundancy principles.

4.1 | Redundancy Principle—H1

Our results indicate that when text is fully redundant with audio (text-and-audio condition), outcomes remain comparable to audio-only, aligning with Adesope and Nesbit's (2012) finding that duplicating written and spoken content need not hinder learning. In their meta-analysis, the authors also emphasise that presenting verbal material in both audio format and text format, but in summary form, can support learning better than presenting the same information in audio-only format or in completely redundant audio and text format. These results were

TABLE 10 | Discriminant Validity: Heterotrait–Monotrait Ratio of Correlations (HTMT).

Construct	Condition modality	ICL	Number of attempts
Condition Modality	—		
ICL	0.21	—	
Number of attempts	0.25	0.36	—

Note: Discriminant validity was assessed with the Heterotrait–Monotrait Ratio of Correlations (HTMT). Values below 0.85 are recommended when constructs are conceptually distinct, whereas a more liberal cutoff of 0.90 can be used for highly related constructs (Hair et al. 2021). Abbreviations: condition modality = condition where the modality principle has been applied; ICL = intrinsic cognitive load; number of attempts = number of folding attempts assisted by AR.

TABLE 11 | Loadings for latent and emergent variables.

Indicator	Condition modality	ICL	Number of attempts	Folding success
ICL1		0.86		
ICL2		0.77		
ICL5		0.69		
Condition modality	1.000			
Number of attempts			1.000	
Guided				0.96
Retention				0.67
Transfer 1				0.56
Transfer 2				0.45
Transfer 3				0.20

Note: Latent, emergent and observed variables: A latent variable is usually an unobservable variable that is supposed to determine the covariation of the describing items. In our dataset intrinsic cognitive load is a latent variable. Loadings for latent variables should range between 0.7 and 0.9 to suggest that the latent variable is well described by the items. An emergent variable is determined by the items describing it. In our dataset the ‘folding success’ emergent variable is determined by the success rate obtained for the guided learning and the retention and transfer tasks. Loadings above 0.5 suggest a strong impact of the variable on the final emergent variable, values below 0.5 could also be potentially removed. In our case the guided learning and the retention task strongly describe the participant performance. The three transfer tasks were lower but still relevant for the final student success rate. Finally, observed variables like the condition assigned to the participants and the number of attempts are by definition perfectly describing themselves and thus have a loading of 1.
 Abbreviations: ICL1 = item 1 from intrinsic cognitive load sub-scale; ICL2 = item 2 from intrinsic cognitive load sub scale; ICL5 = item 5 from intrinsic cognitive load subscale.

also confirmed in the study conducted by Yue et al. (2013), who clearly demonstrated that audio-only presentation of material is significantly worse than any material combining images and audio or images, audio, and text, but that again the combination of images, audio, and summary text is actually the most effective for supporting learning. Therefore, we can state that in our experiment, presenting a redundant text also did not hinder learning outcomes and cognitive load levels. Consequently, the results obtained in this study supported our first hypothesis.

4.2 | Modality Principle (H2–H4)

To support these hypotheses, we tested a model to strengthen the relationship between modality principle, ICL, and learning outcomes. Participants assigned to conditions where the modality principle was applied experienced significantly lower levels of ICL (H2), which in turn led to significantly fewer attempts to learn the procedure (H3) and a significantly higher success rate in the folding task (H3). The hypothesis regarding the negative impact of the number of attempts on performance (H4) was not supported, although it showed the expected direction; in other words, those who needed to listen to the instructions more times were indeed those who had more difficulty with the T-shirt folding performance, although this did not reach statistical significance.

While these results are largely consistent with the existing literature on traditional media, these should be read in light of findings in the context of immersive technologies, especially of VR. In fact, recently a modality reversal effect was tested when using immersive VR (Albus and Seufert 2023). The authors offered possible explanations and according to previous studies (Baceviciute et al. 2021) immersion was considered as a possible boundary condition for the modality principle. In

FIGURE 9 | SEM results. Condition modality = condition where the modality principle was applied; folding success = success or failure in folding the T-shirt in all the tasks; ICL = intrinsic cognitive load; number of attempts = number of attempts before folding the T-shirt. f^2 interpretation: $f^2 \geq 0.02 \rightarrow$ small effect size; $f^2 \geq 0.15 \rightarrow$ medium effect size; $f^2 \geq 0.35 \rightarrow$ large effect size.

TABLE 12 | Direct and indirect effects of the model based on 5000 bootstrap resamples.

Effect type	Path	β	SE	t	p (2-sided)	p (1-sided)
Direct	Condition modality → ICL	−0.210	0.11	−1.89	0.058	0.029
	ICL → Number of attempts	0.362	0.10	3.70	<0.001	<0.001
	ICL → Folding success	−0.507	0.14	−3.54	<0.001	<0.001
	Number of attempts → Folding success	−0.153	0.14	−1.12	0.263	0.131
Indirect	Condition modality → Number of attempts	−0.076	0.05	−1.53	0.125	0.063
	Condition modality → Folding success	0.118	0.07	1.78	0.076	0.038
	ICL → Folding success	−0.055	0.06	−0.98	0.326	0.163

Note: A direct path is a path directly indicated by the researcher when testing the model. An indirect path is a path not directly tested by the researcher. In this case, all the direct paths were significant, and the indirect path Condition Modality → Folding success suggests that the experimental condition alone, without considering the ICL, could have a one-sided significant impact on participants' folding success.

TABLE 13 | Bayesian ANOVA comparing all conditions—continuous variables.

Variable	Mean audio	Mean text	Mean text & audio	BF_{01} (ANOVA)	BF_{01} (audio vs. text)	BF_{01} (text vs. text & audio)
GD	89.2	84.9	88.1	0.60	0.22	0.58
RT	82.5	78.2	80.4	5.83	2.53	3.59
TR1	74.9	77.4	78.9	2.39	2.17	2.94
TR2	77.2	82.5	78.2	2.41	1.12	1.40
TR3	82.8	77.1	82.4	4.22	2.02	2.27

Note: Bayes factor interpretation: $1 < BF_{01} < 3$ anecdotal support for the null hypothesis; $BF_{01} \geq 3$ moderate support for the null hypothesis. Abbreviations: GD = folding accuracy in the guided task; RT = folding accuracy in the retention task; TR1 = folding accuracy in the first transfer task; TR2 = folding accuracy in the second transfer task; TR3 = folding accuracy in the third transfer task.

other words, in immersive scenarios the modality principle could be ineffective or even reversed. Looking at our results and revising the paper that failed in testing the modality principle we supposed that the results obtained in the studies by Albus and Seufert (2023) and Baceviciute et al. (2021) may not be due to the use of immersive technology but rather to the perceived ICL. In Baceviciute's study, a modality reversal effect was observed for the retention task. Although the text-only condition did not produce significant differences, the descriptive statistics indicate that the text-only and text-and-audio conditions were very similar to each other and markedly superior to the audio-only condition. The perceived ICL levels were slightly above the median for all three experimental conditions, indicating that the learning material was complex for participants, though not extremely so. Consistent with this pattern, Albus and Seufert observed the reversal effect for both retention and transfer tasks, with participants perceiving the task complexity as very high. In this case, having the ability to re-read the content multiple times may have constituted an effective advantage for participants. These findings support the key hypothesis: the higher the ICL levels, the greater the probability of observing a reversed modality principle, where text presentation becomes more beneficial than audio presentation. In both cases, the results reported by these studies can be explained in light of the perceived ICL complexity (Leahy and Sweller 2011). Similar considerations cannot be made for the study conducted by Liberman and Dubovi (2022), as they did not measure perceived ICL levels but only electrodermal activity levels, which do not provide an indication of

how subjectively complex participants perceived the learning material to be. Finally, the results obtained in the study conducted by Çeken and Taşkın (2024) were also consistent in non-immersive AR: the modality principle was effective only for the low-complexity task (lightning formation) and not for the more complex task (cell structure). In our study, the ICL levels were well below the median, which may explain why we observed the traditional modality effect rather than a reversal. The application of the segmenting principle as well as the task itself contributed to maintaining low complexity levels, allowing the modality principle to function as predicted. In light of the literature just discussed and of the results presented, it is possible to offer an interpretation of what was observed in the previous studies: the modality principle is highly sensible to task complexity, the task chosen for the VR studies discussed were perceived by the participants as very difficult. It is possible that this is why the participants preferred learning from a text rather than from a narration. Given these considerations, it could be reasonable to think that the immersion provided by the VR environment did not directly affect the modality principle. These results should, however, also be read in light of those reported in the meta-analysis conducted by Ginns (2005). When the task is perceived as very simple, the way in which information is provided becomes almost entirely irrelevant. At the same time, however, when information is highly complex, having the opportunity to reread it becomes advantageous and leads to the reversed modality effect. This suggests a curvilinear relationship between ICL and the effectiveness of the modality principle: when ICL is

very low, all presentation formats yield similar high performance, making the modality principle less relevant. As ICL increases to moderate levels, the advantage of audio over text becomes pronounced, with the modality principle showing its maximum effectiveness. However, as ICL continues to rise towards high levels, this advantage diminishes and eventually reverses, with text-only presentation becoming superior as it allows learners to reread complex material at their own pace.

Given the supposed relevance of the task complexity, it is also worth discussing the task complexity in the procedure proposed in our study. Starting from the success rate we can see that almost all the participants (90%) succeeded in learning the procedure and that almost two attempts were needed before succeeding. Furthermore, the participants reported low levels of perceived ICL (2.9/9 for the text only condition and 2.35 for the other two conditions). These data seem to suggest that the proposed procedure was too easy for them. On the other hand, the participants spent 240s on average (4 min) for learning a procedure that takes literally 2s to perform, once mastered. Excluding the time viewing the learning materials (2 min for the audio version) they still spent two extra minutes learning the procedure. This already suggests that the load they had to face was not really low and the performance itself not so spontaneous. Also the learning trajectory seems to suggest that the participants cannot access to consolidate schemas and had to learn this specific procedure: indeed, performance decreased from the guided learning to the retention task, and decreased even more from retention to the three transfer tasks—exactly as happens when facing newly acquired schemas (see e.g., in the study by Paas and van Merriënboer 1994). Finally looking at perceived ICL: Çeken and Taşkın (2024) tested two very well known learning materials: lightning formation and cell structure. The perceived ICL were 3.49 out of 11 for the first task and 4.64 for the cell structure. If we consider the ICL levels for the text only condition in our experiment (2.9 out of 9), with a simple proportion, we can see that our score when converted in an 11 points scale is 3.54—not so far from the lightning formation score in Çeken and Taşkın's (2024) study. Interestingly for the cell structure learning material the modality principle was not tested. Furthermore, the same procedure adopted in this study was already used (Candido et al. 2025); on that occasion, although the focus was on ECL rather than on ICL, we demonstrated that using AR is less effective than watching a video to learn the procedure. This result would be impossible in the case of a ceiling effect (and therefore in case the task were too easy). These data combined with the results obtained from the tested model seem to suggest that the chosen task was in the sweet spot where the modality principle is actually effective, essentially an easy but not trivial task.

Nevertheless, we want to highlight that our interpretation of the modality principle in immersive technologies cannot be inferred from our data alone. Our study considered a procedural task and used animation as a medium; as is well known, the modality principle is more effective when applied to animations when compared to static images (Schnotz 2021). Therefore, the fact that we found support for the modality principle in our task could also be due to the procedural nature of the task. This should be considered as a possible line of interpretation of the observed results and should open the

discussion for further studies that, together with ours, can contribute to demonstrate that no differences are preventable when using immersive technologies. Furthermore, task complexity should play a more central role when designing learning materials using the modality principle.

4.3 | Folding Accuracy—Control Hypothesis—H5

Finally, hypothesis H5 was only partially confirmed. Although the accuracy with which the T-shirt was folded depended almost entirely on the animations, participants in the audio-only and text & audio conditions still performed significantly better than those in the text-only condition when assisted by AR. However, this result was not confirmed in the retention and transfer tasks. Receiving verbal instructions via audio possibly allowed participants to better visualise the animations during the guided task execution, resulting in greater precision; however, this was insufficient to guarantee better results in the retention and transfer tasks. Although our experiment had different objectives, these results can be interpreted in light of Castro-Alonso et al. (2015) study. In their first experiment, which compared animations versus static images for procedural learning, participants who viewed animations performed better on the first attempt than those who viewed static images, but this effect disappeared completely on the second performance. Notably, their participants received no verbal instructions. This parallels our study, where verbal instructions were irrelevant for determining task accuracy. Therefore, participants in our auditory instruction conditions may have better visualised the animations than those in the text condition, but the advantage animations provide for procedural learning was lost upon task repetition, as in Castro-Alonso et al. (2015) findings.

4.4 | Limitations and Future Studies

This study has some limitations. First, only male participants were included—reflecting the VET population—which may limit generalisability. This potentially limits the generalisability of the findings. Future studies should include a more gender-balanced sample, as previous research showed that gender could influence the attitude towards technology (Cai et al. 2017) although the effect size. However, it is known that using animations can reduce the differences between men and women in tasks that require a high level of visuospatial skills, such as folding a T-shirt. Although we cannot be certain whether gender differences would have emerged in this study, it is reasonable to think that they would not have been significant (Sanchez and Wiley 2010). Despite being fully compliant with the a posteriori power analysis, the sample size could influence our results: the effect of ICL was one-sided significant, as the reported beta (0.207) was below the actual power achieved in the study (0.244). Additionally, the modality and redundancy principles were tested in a procedural learning task and the selected procedure did not constitute a genuine learning objective for the students involved; tasks with a more explicit educational value should be tested. Moreover, it is unknown whether substantial differences would emerge in different kinds of tasks (e.g., a declarative learning task). Although our study has shown

that with moderate levels of perceived ICL in HMD-AR use, the principles are entirely aligned with theory, the role of immersion may still have an effect on learning outcomes. Finally, although we controlled for students' prior knowledge and the participants were randomly assigned to the experimental conditions, it is very likely that all the participants had already had previous experience with folding tasks. It is possible that previously learned schemata could have been reactivated during the learning phase, thus improving the learning outcomes reported in this study. Further research should test declarative and procedural learning materials using immersive technologies contrasting tasks of different complexity to verify whether what is already known about non-immersive technologies can be confirmed in immersive scenarios.

Finally, despite our criticism that other studies did not fully control for the students' behaviour, theoretically giving them the possibility to read a displayed text as many times as they wanted, we also did not fully control these aspects: integrating eye-tracking techniques in further studies could be a way to cope with this limitation.

4.5 | Implications for Theory and Practise

This study provides empirical evidence on CTML's modality and redundancy principles in HMD-AR contexts. Results show a significant impact of the modality principle on ICL levels ($\beta = 0.207$, $f^2 = 0.05$), aligning with CTML predictions. Despite single-experiment limitations, the findings offer practical guidelines for HMD-AR application development. Unlike VR discrepancies, results support CTML principles' applicability in AR procedural learning. From a theoretical perspective, this study has contributed to examining the role of modality and redundancy principles in the use of immersive technologies. It is possible that previous studies conducted using VR actually reported a reversal of the modality principle not due to the use of immersive technology, but rather due to the perceived complexity of the learning materials. Nevertheless, it is relevant to highlight that, although our results are consistent with the existing literature, our experiment demonstrated the modality efficacy under specific conditions: an experimental scenario with a low-complexity procedural task. Still, further investigations are needed to exclude any possible differences between immersive and non-immersive environments when applying the modality principle. From a practical standpoint, while awaiting more evidence on the optimal way to present verbal materials, this study and those previously conducted suggest that the combined auditory and textual presentation of verbal materials may currently be the safest solution for achieving good learning outcomes.

5 | Conclusions

Overall, this study demonstrates that, unlike some early immersive VR findings (Albus and Seufert 2023; Baceviciute et al. 2021), the modality principle can apply to immersive AR much as it does in traditional media. While this is a single study involving the participants in a low-complexity procedural learning task, our results suggest that the modality and redundancy principles in HMD-AR affect learning and CL levels

similarly to what has been observed with conventional media. Furthermore, we tried to make visible, from a statistical standpoint, the relationship between the modality principle, perceived ICL, and learning outcomes as theoretically described by Mayer (2020). Mayer has often demonstrated the efficacy of the modality principle by reporting improved learning outcomes when the modality principle was applied, but the role of the ICL was often only in the theoretical background and rarely supported by evidence. This contribution provided evidence for the modality principle regarding learning outcomes, but we still lack evidence on its effect on ICL and its relationship with learning outcomes.

Author Contributions

Vito Candido: conceptualization, investigation, writing – original draft, methodology, validation, visualization, writing – review and editing, software, formal analysis, data curation, resources. **Franz Lam:** investigation, data curation. **Dominik Petko:** supervision. **Alberto Cattaneo:** conceptualization, funding acquisition, writing – original draft, methodology, writing – review and editing, software, project administration, data curation, supervision, resources.

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Ethics Statement

This research was retrospectively approved by the ethics committee of SFUVET. At the time of data collection, the committee was still being formed. A request for retrospective review was submitted to the ethics committee on February 17, 2025. The study received official approval on March 5, 2025 (approval number: R_8mE2U5duxoLvY6M).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Annex S1.** Explained Folding Technique.